

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon H2020 innovation action programme under grant agreement 101036683.

TransformAr

Accelerating and upscaling transformational adaptation in
Europe: demonstration of water-related innovation
packages

**Replicable socio-economic impact
assessment tools of transformational
pathways**

Deliverable 3.6

Deliverable Number and Name	D3.6 – Replicable socio-economic impact assessment tools of transformational pathways
Work Package	WP3 – Envisioning transformative pathways for the demonstrators
Dissemination Level	PU
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Date Due	31.01.2024
Date Submitted	31.01.2024
File Name	TransformAr_WP3_D3.6_V1.2
Status	
Reviewed by (if applicable)	Jan Cools (UA), Liuliu Du-Ikonen (LUT)
Suggested citation	/

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This document has been prepared in the framework of the European project TransformAr. This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 innovation action programme under grant agreement no. 101036683.

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1. ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviations	Description
CC; CCA; CCM	Climate Change; Climate change adaptation; Climate change mitigation
ES	Ecosystem service
GHG	Greenhouse gas
GI	Green infrastructure
MCA	Multi-criteria analysis
NBS	Nature-based solutions
NSC(-BM)	Nature Smart Cities (Business Model)
RSP	Region-specific portfolio
SSP	Shared socioeconomic pathways
WP	Work Package
Participant acronym	Description
UA	University of Antwerp
CMCC	Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change
ACTERRA	Acterra
E3M	E3-Modelling
PIK	Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research
VERHAERT	Verhaert
FEUGA	Fundación Empresa-Universidad Gallega
NCSR D	National Center for Scientific Research “Demokritos”
CZU	Czech University of Life Sciences Prague
LUT	LUT University
NTNU	Norwegian University of Science and Technology
UVIGO	University of Vigo
EPSILON	EPSILON
ADEME	ADEME Guadeloupe
WRT	Westcountry Rivers Trust
MEDSEA	Mediterranean Sea and Coast Foundation
CETMAR	Fundación CETMAR: Centro Tecnológico del Mar
LAPP	Lappeenranta Municipality
MOE	Egaleo Municipality
WE	Water Europe
EQY	Euroquality
MOG	Municipality of Gjøvik

2. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report addresses the critical challenges associated with climate change adaptation (CCA) by emphasizing the need for effective planning, financing, and implementation strategies. The increasing frequency and intensity of climate change necessitates a comprehensive understanding of the consequences of CCA initiatives. While the significance of CCA is acknowledged, evaluating the socio-economic impact of adaptation measures remains complex due to the diverse array of strategies and the dynamic nature of ecosystems.

The report identifies existing gaps in tools and methodologies for CCA valuation, emphasizing the need for comprehensive frameworks that consider economic dimensions. The Nature Smart Cities Business model (NSC-BM) is proposed as a tool to address these gaps, facilitating the qualitative, quantitative, and monetary valuation of ecosystem services associated with NBS. The NSC-BM is applied in the case study of Lappeenranta, demonstrating its effectiveness in assessing the added value of NBS.

This report contributes to the evaluation of region-specific portfolios (RSP) and, specifically, NBS. The NSC-BM is a rapid assessment tool to facilitate ecosystem services' valuation (qualitatively, quantitatively, and monetarily). The advantages of the NSC-BM are first and foremost on the micro-level, creating understanding of a single measure on the local environment. This understanding at the lower level is vital to gain insight when evaluating the RSP at a broader macro-level. The integrated macro and micro-level evaluations make it a valuable resource for informed decision-making in the face of a changing climate.

This comprehensive information can feed into cost-benefit analyses, providing understanding of both investment and maintenance cost, and benefits. Though the benefits of NBS are shown in both quantitative and monetary terms, challenges in the assessment process include the exclusion of indirect project costs and uncertainties in maintenance costs. The report highlights the importance of mainstreaming decision-support tools for NBS and emphasizes the need for intuitive and easily communicable tools.

In conclusion, the report contributes to assessing the anticipated impacts of transformative solutions, serving as a vital component of ex ante evaluation. The methodology has potential to be extended beyond individual solutions to enable a comprehensive analysis of RSP. Future research directions involve an ex-post analysis, comparing anticipated outcomes with actual results, supporting an iterative process of learning, refining methodologies, and optimizing decision-making processes.

3. INTRODUCTION

The increasing frequency and intensity of climate change and extreme weather events have far-reaching impacts. Economic losses amount to more than 12 billion EUR per year in the EU on average and, therefore, call for the need to increase our resilience to climate change (European Commission 2021). The challenges to address climate change (CC) are usually qualified as either “adaptation” or “mitigation” responses. Climate change mitigation (CCM) efforts should prevent further contribution to the causes of CC, e.g., through decarbonization of electricity generation. Climate change adaptation (CCA) efforts on the other hand prepare our world for impacts of CC that are currently already felt (e.g. through investment in flood risk control) or potentially exploiting CC effects (e.g. through introducing new crop varieties resistant to changing local climate conditions) (Ginbo, Corato and Hoffmann 2021). The importance of CCA is increasingly recognized, but current actions are deemed insufficient from a planning, financing and implementation perspective (United Nations Environment Programme 2023).

The challenge lies not only in recognizing the importance of CCA and its design but also in comprehensively understanding its consequences (Webler, et al. 2016). Despite the growing recognition of CCA's significance, there exists a complexity in gauging the effectiveness and socio-economic impact of adaptation measures. The diverse array of strategies, ranging from traditional practices like flood risk control to innovative approaches such as resilient crop varieties, poses a challenge in evaluating their outcomes. The dynamic and interconnected nature of ecosystems, coupled with the unpredictability of climate-induced changes, demands an understanding of how adaptation initiatives unfold. To address this challenge, there is an urgent need for evaluation tools that can assess the multi-dimensional impacts of CCA. These tools should not only quantify economic outcomes but also consider ecological, social, and (possibly) cultural dimensions, providing a holistic perspective on the efficacy of adaptation efforts. The development and application of such tools become vital in bridging the gap between recognizing the importance of adaptation and ensuring that actions taken are not only meaningful but also optimally contribute to building resilience in the face of a changing climate.

In accordance with Task 3.5 of WP 3, Acterra leads the creation of a “Transformation action plan and combination of solutions”. In addressing the multifaceted challenge of understanding the consequences of CCA, the concept of “adaptation pathways” emerges as a strategic framework. Using the preferred pathways selected in Task 3.4, Acterra will build an action plan tool. In order to understand this, one needs to define an adaptation pathway, and explain the methodology to select the preferred one.

An adaptation pathway refers to the combination and sequencing of adaptation actions of different types and with different levels of response (some being implemented now, and others reserved for the future) to achieve the objective set by the community in the long term (ADEME 2019). Similarly, Werners, et al. (2021) define adaptation pathways as a sequence of actions that can be progressively implemented, contingent upon the evolving dynamics of future climate conditions. These pathways provide a general roadmap for decision-makers and planners, offering flexibility to adjust strategies as the future unfolds. For the TransformAr project, pathways are sequenced into four levels of impact (low, medium, high, very high), with established thresholds deciding the transition from one impact level to another.

Acterra, in collaboration with demonstrator territories will establish a qualitative multi-criteria analysis (MCA) based on the assessment of pathways and solutions identified using criteria such as efficiency, effectiveness, feasibility, social acceptance, and durability/viability. The quantitative assessment led

by UA in the framework of the Task 3.4 will complement this qualitative assessment approach of the pathways. The combination of those two approaches will lead to the selection of the preferred pathway for every demonstrator.

In this report, our approach extends beyond the macro-level evaluation of climate adaptation pathways to encompass a nuanced understanding at the micro-economic level. We propose a feasibility assessment to evaluate NBS as individual measures, complementing our broader efforts in the evaluation of a region-specific portfolio (RSP). This report, through its case study in the municipality of Lappeenranta (Finland), contributes to the quantitative evaluation of climate adaptation pathways. This micro-level assessment not only enables the evaluation of the economic implications of specific actions but also supports informed decision-making by providing insights into the financial viability of individual measures.

By bridging the macro and micro perspectives, our comprehensive evaluation framework aims to enhance the precision and efficacy of climate change adaptation strategies. This integrative approach acknowledges the importance of assessing both overarching pathways and the detailed economic implications of specific actions. As we delve into the evaluation of individual measures, we recognize the narrow scope of such analysis, implying it may not directly yield a full evaluation of adaptation pathways within the context of a RSP. This underscores the need for continued efforts in comprehending the interaction effects between different solutions in a RSP in future deliverables.

4. EXISTING TOOLS AND METHODOLOGIES FOR CCA VALUATION

Current status

The assessment of CCA strategies is a complex endeavor, requiring robust tools and methodologies that span both biophysical and economic dimensions. While numerous tools exist to model and plan urban environments, a critical gap persists in the incorporation of economic values, highlighting a significant knowledge deficit in current research. Many existing frameworks primarily focus on the biophysical features of environments, neglecting the essential economic considerations necessary for comprehensive climate adaptation planning (Van Oijstaeijen, Van Passel and Cools 2020). This deficiency hinders the ability to fully comprehend the economic implications of adaptation measures, limiting the effectiveness of decision-making processes.

Moreover, a pronounced gap exists in addressing the cost side of valuation toolkits. The inadequacy in understanding the economic costs associated with CCA measures illustrates a notable shortfall in existing research efforts. Without an understanding of the economic dimensions, local authorities face challenges in bridging the gap between high-level policy goals and operational implementation. This gap within (local) authorities has been documented in various studies (Bush 2020; Raynor, Mayere and Matthews 2017; Van Oijstaeijen, Finizola e Silva, et al. 2023), emphasizing the need for tools and methodologies that provide a more holistic and integrated approach to valuation.

The existing landscape also reveals a significant disparity within (local) authorities concerning the alignment of strategic vision and operational implementation dimensions. The struggle to fully commit to policies' high-level goals, objectives, and ambitions is a recurring theme in the literature. This disconnect can impede the effective implementation of climate change adaptation measures, hindering the realization of overarching objectives.

Additionally, the literature on NBS emphasizes the need for improved valuation methodologies. While NBS presents a promising avenue for sustainable adaptation, existing tools often fall short in adequately capturing the economic values associated with these solutions. Closing this valuation gap is crucial for promoting the widespread adoption of NBS in climate change adaptation strategies.

In conclusion, a comprehensive evaluation of climate change adaptation strategies necessitates tools and methodologies that address the cost knowledge gap, bridge the disparity between strategic vision and operational implementation, and enhance the valuation of NBS. By addressing these gaps, researchers and practitioners can develop more effective and economically informed strategies, ensuring the successful implementation of climate adaptation measures at both strategic and operational levels. In the next subsection, we propose the Nature Smart Cities Business model (NSC-BM) as a tool that provides a more holistic and integrated approach to valuation.

Nature Smart Cities

Assessing the costs and benefits of NBS remains challenging. While a number of tools, databases and online portals exist on the added value of NBS, it is in practice demanding for local authorities to evaluate the costs and benefits. The challenge arises from the intricate nature of ecosystem services and the constraints of resources, encompassing both expertise and time, particularly at the local level. Hence, tools that streamline this process can contribute to its facilitation. Van Oijstaeijen, Van Passel and Cools (2020) evaluated several of these (economic) valuation tools from the perspective of

applicability for local officers to optimize GI or NBS projects. This evaluation was based on 13 criteria. Table 1 shows both the list of evaluated tools and the evaluation criteria.

Valuation toolkits	Evaluation criteria
Nature Value Explorer (NVE)	Type of green infrastructure
i-Tree eco	Subject of valuation
Green infrastructure valuation toolkit (GI-Val)	Time Requirement
A guide to value Green Infrastructure	Expertise Requirement
Toolkit for Ecosystem Service Site-based Assessment (TESSA)	Economic Soundness
Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services and Tradeoffs (InVEST)	Biophysical Soundness
EcoPLAN Scenario Evaluator (SE)	Quantification
Green Infrastructure Benefits Valuation Tool	Uncertainty
Capital Asset Value of Amenity Trees (CAVAT)	Adaptability
Benefits Estimation Tool (BEST)	Generalizability
	Scalability
	Scenario Analysis

Table 1 Overview of valuation toolkits and their evaluation criteria (Van Oijstaeijen, Van Passel and Cools 2020).

The results of this assessment fed the development of a novel tool, developed in the interreg-2seas Nature Smart Cities project, and published by Van Oijstaeijen, Finizola e Silva, et al. (2023). The tool was initially designed for small-scale and urban nature-based solutions or green infrastructure in the 2 seas area (Belgium, the Netherlands, northern France, and the UK). However, several of the barriers to widespread GI or NBS uptake appear to be general. One of these barriers is the limited understanding of the impacts of NBS, and how these can be assessed. This can range from small-scale urban NBS, but extends to flood risk and river basin management, climate adaptation, and biodiversity conservation and restoration. With this case study, we, therefore, aim to contemplate the potential and limitations of economic project appraisal utilizing the NSC-BM beyond its geographical boundaries. This process contributes to assessing the generalizability capacity. Further, we aim to identify pathways to – rather than reinventing the wheel – iteratively improve the valuation methods to extend their scope and validate the tool’s methods. After all, the key to successful implementation (at local authorities) of socio-economic valuation tools for NBS relies on credibility, usability, and comprehensiveness (Back 2021).

The NSC-BM is a rapid assessment tool to facilitate ecosystem services’ valuation (qualitatively, quantitatively, and monetarily). This comprehensive information can feed into cost-benefit analyses. In the next section, we apply the NSC-BM to a proposed NBS solution in Lappeenranta. Application outside of this area was not attempted earlier, hence the motivation to test the tool on this demonstrator.

5. CASE STUDY: LAPPEENRANTA

Introduction to Lappeenranta

Figure 1 Location of the Lappeenranta demonstrator.

The Lappeenranta case covers approximately **1750 m² of urbanized land**, located in Koulukatu street. The area which is subject to the NBS investment is in a **residential area**, characterized by medium-high apartment buildings (+/- 4 floors). In total, an area of 245 m² will be transformed into an infiltration area. This infiltration area is objectified to **relieve some of the water stress in the area**, especially regarding floodings. Originally, the area was composed of a combination of green (grass, trees) and grey (footpath, road) elements, the details of which are filled out in the next step. The new spatial design results in **470 m² of surface area that will be disconnected from the sewage system**. In this case study, the application of the NSC-BM¹ is demonstrated step-by-step, following the BM flow depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 2 Construction of the demonstrator in Koulukatu, Lappeenranta.

¹ The applied NSC-BM tool can be downloaded from the [Nature Smart Cities page](#) on the website of the University of Antwerp. The tool is accessible as an offline Excel file, employing macros to assist users in navigating through various stages of the assessment. First, the tool must be saved on the user's computer. Next, utilizing the application necessitates users' ability to enable macros.

After downloading and saving the Excel file, users are advised to download the step-by-step guide, which is available from the same webpage. This guide explains at every step what the user is expected to do, and which data is required for the successful completion of this step.

Further, a clear insight into the project site's characteristics is required. This implies that the user needs data on the project's area and the current land cover.

Figure 3 NSC-BM flow of steps and worksheets.

Application of the NSC-BM tool

Step 0: Project description

Figure 4 Surface area (1758 m²) from Google Earth Pro.

In the first step of the assessment, project sites are defined in terms of land cover types. We defined three different spatial scenarios: the baseline scenario, the NBS scenario, and the hypothetical grey scenario (see Figure 5).

Defining your (public) green/blue/grey infrastructure					
Scenario title	Tot. scenario area	Category	Type	Amount	Unit
Baseline Scenario	1758 m ²	Trees and Shrubs	Single tree (>12m)	3	amount
		Trees and Shrubs	Single tree (6m-12m)	4	amount
		Grey infrastructure	Impermeable surface	1465	m ²
		Low Green	Lawn	293	m ²
		Sustainable drainage systems	Filter drain or infiltration trench	41	m ²
Lappeenranta NBS	1758 m ²	Low Green	Tall grass	100	m ²
		Low Green	Flower field	90	m ²
		Trees and Shrubs	Shrubby plants	14	m ²
		Trees and Shrubs	Single tree (6m-12m)	8	amount
		Low Green	Lawn	35	m ²
		Grey infrastructure	Impermeable surface	1478	m ²
		Other	Biochar		
		Grey infrastructure	Impermeable surface	1758	m ²
Lappeenranta Grey	1758 m ²	Grey infrastructure	Impermeable surface	1758	m ²

Figure 5 Step 0 of the Lappeenranta case in the NSC-BM.

In the **baseline scenario** we take the characteristics of the landscape as they were before the NBS investment was to be implemented. The **second scenario, Lappeenranta NBS, features the outlook of the area in the future, resulting from the NBS investment.** Noticeably, a large share of the initial lawn is transformed into a diverse infiltration area, containing a small infiltration trench, and a larger border containing trees, flowers, tall grasses, and bushes. It can be noted that there's a slight increase in grey, impermeable surface, which is due to the net surface area of the footpath being slightly higher, although this effect is negligible. **The third scenario, Lappeenranta grey, is purely hypothetical, envisioning a streetscape composed entirely of grey elements.** This speculative scenario aims to underscore the influence of greenery on a relatively modest surface area considered within this analysis.

Step 1: Selection

In the second step, users indicate which ecosystem services matter for the project, or are indicated as important by the municipality (e.g., towards sustainability targets). Based on the input from officers from the city of Lappeenranta **water retention and infiltration, habitat for biodiversity, and aesthetic appreciation** are prioritized. These were complemented with the ecosystem services **carbon sequestration, and air filtering**, as those are commonly considered in the context of infrastructure valuation and climate change. These were added to also demonstrate how a focus on certain ecosystem services might also yield significant impacts on other ecosystem services. By highlighting these, the results might contribute to generating more holistic cross-disciplinary solutions.

Step 2: Parameters selection

Based on the ES that were indicated in Step 1, users are expected to complete this step with **a few parameters of the area to improve the calculations of the tool.** For carbon sequestration and air filtering no additional parameters are required. For water retention and infiltration, the yearly average precipitation in the area was needed. The area consists of 470 m² of surrounding impermeable surface area that is disconnected from the sewage system, and another 495 m² of the footpath that will also release stormwater into the infiltration area. This yields a total of 965 m² outside of the infiltration area that is relieved of stormwater runoff (see Figure 6). The habitat for biodiversity is assessed in a separate worksheet (see Habitat for biodiversity). For aesthetic appreciation the tool incorporates how many residents are impacted by the spatial changes.

ESS	Necessary data for calculations	BASELINE SCENARIO	LAPPEENRANTA NBS	LAPPEENRANTA GREY
Carbon sequestration	/// No additional parameters necessary for calculation (if 'S0: Project description' has been filled in) ///			
Water retention and infiltration (Worksheet "A - Water retention" can be used for calculation)	Average precipitation per year in m3 per m2	0,614	0,614	0,614
	Do you intend to collect water from outside of the project area (e.g. surrounding roofs)?	NO	YES	NO
	If you answered 'yes' to the previous question, how large is the surface area of the roofs/streets you will collect water from? (m ²)	0	965	0
Air filtering	/// No additional parameters necessary for calculation (if 'S0: Project description' has been filled in) ///			
Habitat for biodiversity	See tab 'C-Biodiversity' for biodiversity assessment, tab (B-Biodiversity will be filled in for you)	(Fill in tab B and C)	(Fill in tab B and C)	(Fill in tab B and C)
Aesthetic appreciation	Number of residents living in or around (max 100m radius) the project area	100	100	100

Figure 6 Step 2 from the Lappeenranta case in the NSC-BM.

Habitat for biodiversity

The assessment of habitat for biodiversity is twofold. In the first biodiversity worksheet (*B - Biodiversity*) the **structural variation** of the site is analyzed using the Shannon-Weaver index. The higher the Shannon-Weaver index, the more diversity is incorporated in the landscape, and, therefore, **the higher the potential for species to habitat in this area**. In Figure 7, we see that the **Shannon-Weaver index** (displayed under the heading 'D') **doubles from the baseline scenario to the NBS scenario**. Intuitively, an all-grey scenario would yield no potential for habitat whatsoever. The second biodiversity worksheet (*C - biodiversity*) assesses the habitat potential for specific species of birds, butterflies, bees, and amphibians based on the landscape elements present in the project area. The results of this assessment are displayed in the next step (*Step 3 – Quantification*).

STRUCTURAL VARIATION							
BASELINE SCENARIO							
	Surface area (in m2)		Log(surface area)		H'	Hmax	D
Layers					0,681179504	0,693147181	1,976207302
Lawn & Amenity Grassland	293	0,363970008	2,46686762				
Overgrown	0	FALSE	FALSE				
Tall grass	0	FALSE	FALSE				
Flower field	0	FALSE	FALSE				
Middle green	0	FALSE	FALSE				
Trees	400	0,317209496	2,602059991				
Water elements	0	FALSE	FALSE				
Semi-permeable	0	FALSE	FALSE				
Allotment garden	0	FALSE	FALSE				
Other	0	FALSE	FALSE				
LAPPEENRANTA NBS							
	Surface area		Log(surface area)		H'	Hmax	D
Layers					1,384776538	1,791759469	3,993933311
Lawn & Amenity Grassland	35	0,170185045	1,544068044				
Overgrown	0	FALSE	FALSE				
Tall grass	100	0,3039822	2				
Flower field	90	0,290046561	1,954242509				
Middle green	14	0,090344973	1,146128036				
Trees	296	0,342120606	2,471291711				
Water elements	41	0,188097152	1,612783857				
Semi-permeable	0	FALSE	FALSE				
Allotment garden	0	FALSE	FALSE				
Other	0	FALSE	FALSE				
LAPPEENRANTA GREY							
	Surface area		Log(surface area)		H'	Hmax	D
Layers					0	FALSE	FALSE
Lawn & Amenity Grassland	0	FALSE	FALSE				
Overgrown	0	FALSE	FALSE				
Tall grass	0	FALSE	FALSE				
Flower field	0	FALSE	FALSE				
Middle green	0	FALSE	FALSE				
Trees	0	FALSE	FALSE				
Water elements	0	FALSE	FALSE				
Semi-permeable	0	FALSE	FALSE				
Allotment garden	0	FALSE	FALSE				
Other	0	FALSE	FALSE				

Figure 7 Worksheet B - Biodiversity output from the NSC-BM.

Step 3: Quantification

The results for the quantifiable ecosystem services are displayed in Figure 8. We see how the NBS scenario yields a **10% increase in yearly sequestered carbon**. Further, it is noticeable that the **water retention and infiltration of the project area has increased by over 200%**, which will meaningfully address the flooding risk in the project area or relieve areas downstream from experiencing pluvial floodings. Additionally, the enhanced landscape diversity and green landscape layers yield improved results for the air filtering capacity of the area when comparing the NBS with the baseline scenario. The habitat for biodiversity graphs display the potential for certain species to make habitat in the project area, the greener the bar, the more species could find a suitable habitat. A significant impact is evident with the NBS scenario, **particularly for certain species of birds and butterflies**. When

compared to the all-grey scenario, the influence of the greener street design on ES delivery at the local scale becomes particularly pronounced.

Figure 8 Step 3 Quantification results from the NSC-BM.

Step 4: Qualification

In this step, the ES that are part of the assessment are scored on a 0 (no contribution) to 3 (excellent contribution to desired ecosystem service level) scale. These scores are translated onto a spider diagram, shown in Figure 9. The red dot in the central illustrates how the all-grey scenario yields no contributions to any of the ecosystem services on display. Comparing the NBS (green) and the baseline scenario (blue), the diagram displays how small improvements are expected on biodiversity, aesthetic appreciation, carbon sequestration, and air filtering. The water retention and infiltration is likely to experience a large increase as a result from NBS scenario, compared to the baseline scenario.

Figure 9 Step 4 Qualification from the NSC-BM.

Step 5a: Monetization (costs)

The cost estimations are based on research in Western Europe (Belgium, France, the Netherlands and UK) at 2022 price levels and are, therefore, less suitable for application in a Finnish context. Local data has been used to adapt these calculations to the Finnish price levels. For these prices, we have not been able to obtain element-specific data. Rather, there are investment and maintenance cost for the overarching categories, e.g., green infrastructure and grey infrastructure. The goal of this exercise is to compare different alternatives and compare monetary costs and benefits *relatively*. The results should not be interpreted as an accurate cost and benefit estimate to be used to estimate the needed financial resources for an alternative.

The **investment costs for the NBS investment** are calculated at €/m². The total investment costs are **€93,100**. However, €10,000 of this total is budgeted for the installation of new groundwater pipes, which is not related to the NBS investment. The remaining €83,100 contains both direct (labor, materials, vegetation, etc.) and indirect costs (overhead, management, etc.). We, therefore, take this construction cost as a custom lump sum amount, not utilizing the built-in ballpark estimations of the tool (see Recommendations based on specific case application in Lappeenranta).

Further, the infiltration area is expected to result in higher maintenance costs than regular green patches in the city. As the maintenance costs are uncertain, we have estimated the impact of this maintenance cost for different magnitudes (50% more maintenance, twice as much maintenance, three times as much maintenance, and 10 times as much maintenance). The maintenance cost is calculated on an annual basis, for a 20-year period and for a 40-year period (discount rate of 3,5%). As can be seen, the expected maintenance costs are very similar if the maintenance of the infiltration area would be comparable to the regular maintenance cost of green infrastructure as used within the city of Lappeenranta. Assuming higher unit prices maintenance costs (150%, 200%, 300%, 1000%, compared to the baseline maintenance cost), there's an annual relative difference of €200, €400, €800, and €3700 compared to the baseline scenario. These estimations allow us to compare with the relative monetized benefits in the following step.

	Surface area green infrastructure in m ² (from Step 0)	Maintenance cost green (in €/m ²)	Surface area grey infrastructure in m ² (from Step 0)	Maintenance cost grey (in €/m ²)	Total annual maintenance cost (in €1.000)	20 years (in €1.000)	40 years (in €1.000)
Baseline scenario	293	1.69	1465	0.93	1.9	27	40
Lappeenranta NBS	280	1.69	1478	0.93	1.8	27	40
Lappeenranta NBS (150% maintenance)	280	2.54	1478	0.93	2.1	30	45
Lappeenranta NBS (200% maintenance)	280	3.38	1478	0.93	2.3	33	49
Lappeenranta NBS (300% maintenance)	280	5.07	1478	0.93	2.7	39	58
Lappeenranta NBS (1000% maintenance)	280	16.90	1478	0.93	5.6	81	121
Lappeenranta grey	0	1.69	1758	0.93	1.6	24	35

Table 2 Maintenance cost in different scenarios.

Step 5b: Monetization (benefits)

Three of the selected ecosystem services can be monetized: carbon sequestration (at actual EU-ETS price), water retention and infiltration (as avoided cost of sewage water treatment), and aesthetic appreciation (as residents' WTP for more enjoyable – greener – living environments). However, in the case of Lappeenranta, stormwater is not transported to stormwater treatment facilities. Instead, it gets discharged into natural water reservoirs. Resultingly, there's no cost avoided because of the NBS, and the value of this avoided cost is therefore set a €0. In this step, the monetized results are presented in annual benefit, for a 20-year period, and for a 40-year period (see Figure 10). It is important to note that **the monetized result only presents a small subset of the actual added value** (see discussion in Recommendations and reflections based on the case study). The annual difference of benefits between baseline and NBS scenarios is around €600. Evidently, the all-grey scenario yields almost €0 in monetized benefits. This value is almost solely the result of the expected improved aesthetic appreciation of the residents in the neighborhood.

BASELINE SCENARIO	Quantified result	Unit value	One-time benefit	Annual benefit	Total Benefit (20yr life span)	Total benefit (40yrs life span)
Carbon sequestration	0,10 tonnes/yr	72,10		7,00	48,22	48,22
Water retention and infiltration	272,78 m3/yr	0,00		0,00	0,00	0,00
Air filtering		CAN NOT BE MONETIZED		-	-	-
Habitat for biodiversity		CAN NOT BE MONETIZED		-	-	-
Aesthetic appreciation	100,00	2,50		250,00	3640,04	5425,08
TOTAL MONETARY BENEFITS BASELINE SCENARIO				257,00	3808,26	5473,30
LAPPEENRANTA NBS	Quantified result	Unit value	One-time benefit	Annual benefit	Total Benefit (20yr life span)	Total benefit (40yrs life span)
Carbon sequestration	0,11 tonnes/yr	72,10		7,79	53,66	53,66
Water retention and infiltration	867,36 m3/yr	0,00		0,00	0,00	0,00
Air filtering		CAN NOT BE MONETIZED		-	-	-
Habitat for biodiversity		CAN NOT BE MONETIZED		-	-	-
Aesthetic appreciation	100,00	8,33		833,33	12133,43	18083,60
TOTAL MONETARY BENEFITS LAPPEENRANTA NBS				841,12	12187,10	18137,27
BASELINE SCENARIO	Quantified result	Unit value	One-time benefit	Annual benefit	Total Benefit (20yr life span)	Total benefit (40yrs life span)
Carbon sequestration	0,00 tonnes/yr	72,10		0,00	0,00	0,00
Water retention and infiltration	21,59 m3/yr	0,00		0,00	0,00	0,00
Air filtering		CAN NOT BE MONETIZED		-	-	-
Habitat for biodiversity		CAN NOT BE MONETIZED		-	-	-
Aesthetic appreciation	100,00	0,00		0,00	0,00	0,00
TOTAL MONETARY BENEFITS				0,00	0,00	0,00

Figure 10 Monetization results from the NSC-BM.

Step 6: Factsheet

The last step in the tool is the extraction of a factsheet. In this factsheet, a summary of the most important elements of the exercise is provided. This provides **a comparative overview between two scenarios**. The three comparative factsheets (Baseline-NBS, Baseline-Grey, and NBS-Grey) are included in Appendix NSC-BM Factsheets for Lappeenranta case study.

Conclusion of the case study

As the project in Lappeenranta is currently described, the case study evaluation through the tool clearly emphasizes the added value of investing in the proposed NBS. Every criterion or ecosystem service that is included in the assessment is likely to improve because of the investment, and their relative importance is illustrated in multiple ways: qualitatively (see spider diagram in Figure 9), quantitatively (Figure 7 and Figure 8), but also monetarily. Therefore, this provides the local authority with multiple arguments to justify a potential investment, which clearly demonstrates the advantage of deploying the NSC-BM on this specific project. Since the monetized arguments might be less intuitive, conclusions that can be drawn of the exercise are established further. Exploring the monetized impact, several conclusions can be drawn.

First, looking at the yearly costs, we see that the maintenance costs always exceed the monetized benefits. However, it is important to emphasize that the monetization of ecosystem services only scratches the surface in terms of total added (societal and ecological) value. Figure 11 explains this in more detail by displaying the valuation pyramid. The pyramid outlines how a substantial portion of the diverse ecosystem services can be conveyed qualitatively. Among these qualitative expressions, a smaller subset can then be translated into quantitative terms. Ultimately, only a fraction of these values can be articulated in monetary units. Hence, these absolute values should be construed as indicative, preferably discussed in a comparative manner (e.g., observing that the value generated through NBS is twice as much as the baseline scenario). A concrete example can be conveyed through the added value of the local water infiltration and retention. While the tool values this at avoided costs of stormwater treatment, the component of avoided damage costs of flooding is not monetized, and thus economically not valued in the current assessment.

Figure 11 The valuation pyramid (ten Brink 2008).

Second, the (construction) cost calculations in the tool focus on direct investment cost (e.g., building materials). Given the high variability in indirect project costs (e.g., preparatory works, overhead, etc.), these are not included in the cost calculations of the NSC-BM. This is a likely explanation for the large difference between the estimated project costs by Lappeenranta's government officials and the outcomes of the application of the tool. Still, we believe the tool to be highly valuable and applicable, under the precondition of using it as an instrument to compare scenarios. The relative costs are far more informative than the absolute values, since these indirect costs are not accounted for.

Third, the difference in monetized benefits (NBS vs. baseline) exceeds the difference in estimated maintenance costs. However, since there is uncertainty on the maintenance costs of the infiltration area (it is assumed that these will require more intensive maintenance), we explored the impact of varying unit prices on the aggregate estimated annual maintenance costs. Comparing these with the difference in monetized benefits, we find that the latter (€600) exceeds additional maintenance costs if the infiltration area is less than +2.5 times as maintenance-intensive as regular green infrastructure. To illustrate this, we analyze the yearly estimated *cash-flow* (i.e., yearly benefits minus yearly costs). Here, we find that the *cash-flow* in the baseline scenario would be equal to a loss of €1600 annually (€257 - €1857 = €-1600). If the maintenance cost of the infiltration area in the NBS is 2.5 higher, the *cash-flow* would yield a similar loss of €1627,8 (€841 - €2468.8). **Resultingly, we can say that – in monetary terms – even if the infiltration area is two and a halve times as maintenance-intensive, it is still desirable to invest in the NBS.**

6. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR IMPLEMENTATION

In reflection of the case study conducted in Lappeenranta, we have identified several notable advantages of the cost-benefit tool, along with specific areas for improvement. One key strength is the tool's accessibility, as it is easily understood. This simplicity has facilitated effective communication among stakeholders, fostering collaboration and understanding. Furthermore, the tool has successfully provided valuable insights into the cost implications of NBS, a critical factor in the decision-making process. Given that the costs associated with NBS remain a relatively new and sensitive topic for government officials, the tool's ability to present clear and comprehensible cost information is a significant asset.

A rapid assessment of ecosystem services before investing in a NBS offers crucial advantages in the decision-making process. Firstly, it provides stakeholders with a preliminary understanding of the potential benefits and drawbacks associated with the proposed NBS. This initial assessment helps in estimating the overall impact on ecosystem services, guiding decision-makers in determining the feasibility and suitability of the investment. Furthermore, a rapid assessment allows for the identification of key ecosystem services that may be enhanced or compromised by the NBS. This insight aids in tailoring the nature-based intervention to align with specific environmental and community needs, optimizing its positive effects. Additionally, by evaluating ecosystem services early in the planning phase, potential conflicts or unintended consequences can be identified, enabling proactive adjustments to the NBS design to mitigate risks and enhance overall effectiveness.

The evaluation of a NBS provides more than just insights into its individual costs and benefits. It inherently contributes to the valuation of a broader adaptation pathway. By understanding the economic implications and ecosystem service outcomes of the NBS within a specific geographical context, decision-makers gain valuable information that can be extrapolated to assess the overall effectiveness of the chosen adaptation pathway. The NBS case study is as a quantitative evaluation within the larger landscape of climate change adaptation strategies and a demonstrator's RSP. Lessons learned and insights gained from this specific measure enrich the understanding of how such nature-based interventions can be strategically integrated into comprehensive adaptation pathways, providing a foundation for informed, strategic, and economically viable climate adaptation planning at a broader scale.

However, as with any tool, there are areas that warrant refinement and enhancement. First, the habitat for biodiversity assessment that depicts the impact on certain species might not provide accurate results for the geographical area of the demonstrator. Since the assessment is based on species in the 2seas area (Belgium, the Netherlands, France and the United Kingdom), different bird, butterfly and amphibian species might need to be subjected to a similar analysis. However, the tool complements this by also showing the Shannon-Weaver index for the project. We clearly see how this index doubles as a result of the NBS investment. This doubling implies a 100% improvement on the species' variation in the project area, which amply improves the possibility of species to find a habitat or migration route as a result of the investment. The reflection and feedback on the results did demonstrate that such results (conform the Shannon-Weaver index) are predictable. Further, it was mentioned that a target species analysis – as is currently only available for the 2seas area – would be highly valuable for local authorities to have access to. This would provide tangible biodiversity results, which can contribute to monitoring and communication purposes.

The geographical context introduces additional dimensions for enhancing the tool's comprehensiveness, particularly in addressing water retention and infiltration. Lappeenranta

experiences a substantial portion of its precipitation as snow, introducing uncertainty regarding the influence of snow on the retention coefficient across different spatial layers. Simultaneously, considering the pertinent flood risk in the area adds another layer of significance. To achieve a better understanding of these geographical aspects and their impact on specific ecosystem services, it is important to integrate additional scientific research into the tool's framework. This research will be instrumental in uncovering the complex relationships between snowfall, flood risk, and the outcomes of the ecosystem services under consideration.

Moreover, potential biases can arise from the use of the general data in the data library instead of more recent, localized cost data. The NSC-BM's data library often relies on stated and revealed preference methods specific to certain geographical areas. While this information may closely reflect reality in urbanized regions within the 2seas area, adjustments may be necessary for users applying the tool on a broader geographical scale. Consequently, a cautious approach to the tool's application beyond its intended area is advised. However, this does not imply that utilizing the tool for the NBS case is futile. The tool is intended to provide rapid estimations and ball-park figures, and so the relative values always contribute to better understanding the impact of green infrastructures or NBS on the provision of ecosystem services. The NSC-BM can consistently serve as a benchmark with a general estimate for planning and design.

7. CHALLENGES AND DIRECTIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

Ex-post valuation

This deliverable plays a crucial role in our ongoing efforts to assess the anticipated impacts of our transformative solutions, serving as an integral component of the ex-ante evaluation. The methodology goes beyond individual solutions, extending its scope to enable potential comprehensive analysis of RSP. Our focus here is on predicting and forecasting the expected costs, encompassing both investment and maintenance, as well as the anticipated benefits, such as ecosystem services and risk reduction, specifically related to the stormwater management solution in Lappeenranta.

By providing insights into various scenarios, the results of this deliverable aim to offer a comprehensive overview, facilitating the decision-making process. The knowledge and experience acquired from this phase will serve as the foundation for our subsequent work in Deliverable D5.2 (titled: Sustainability Profiles of Solutions). This upcoming deliverable will delve into the ex-post assessment, employing a cost-benefit analysis to qualitatively and quantitatively evaluate the solutions and RSP.

In D5.2, we will compare the anticipated outcomes from the ex-ante analysis with the actual results obtained, facilitating a deeper understanding of any disparities. This comparative analysis will empower us to learn, refine our methodology, and implement necessary adjustments. This iterative process is fundamental for the continual enhancement of our decision-making processes. In essence, the collaborative synergy between D3.6 and D5.2 is strategically designed to seamlessly connect predictive and retrospective viewpoints, supporting an ongoing cycle of prediction, action, and evaluation to optimize the effectiveness of our future decision-making processes.

Decision-making and uncertainty

This deliverable is focused on the valuation of CCA measures. This can be extended to decision-making under uncertainty, meaning the decision whether to implement a CCA measure accounting for risks and uncertainties. From the decision making point of view of public authorities (local up to international level), CC(A) has some features that can make it difficult to deal with: i) reactive or incremental adaptations (e.g. farmers adapt to shift in growing season) might not be sufficient, therefore anticipatory and coordinated adaptation is required (Buurman and Babovic, 2016; Dittrich, Wreford and Moran, 2016), ii) it requires an upfront investment with benefits that need to materialize over time, are do not necessarily immediately, iii) policy makers have a tendency to focus on the short term (e.g. decision horizon limited to the next election round for decision makers in a political context), iv) competition of CC actions with other issues (Dittrich, Wreford and Moran 2016), v) different aspects of uncertainty, vi) the potential for lock-in effects for some CC investments which, when combined with uncertainty, creates an incentive to postpone investments to wait for further information (Ginbo, Corato and Hoffmann 2021). The uncertainty of CC is characterized in many forms: it relates to a lack of knowledge of physical systems, their impacts, the human response to CC, future evolution of technology and downscaling impacts from global to local level, with the risk of being over- or under adapted (Dittrich, Wreford and Moran 2016). This in turn can lead to additional costs, overinvestment or the failure to seize new opportunities arising from CC (Dittrich, Wreford and Moran 2016).

Dittrich, Wreford and Moran (2016) provide an overview of decision making tools in the context of CCA. Traditional decision making approaches (e.g. cost-benefit analysis, cost-effectiveness analysis) and multi criteria analysis) have difficulties to properly evaluate solutions for CCA, especially in tackling some aspects of uncertainty. Therefore, both in policy and academic context alternatives are being explored under the umbrella of “robust decision making approaches”. The common feature of these

approaches is the aim to “optimize across scenarios”, rather than “optimizing one scenario” as is the case in the more traditional approaches (Dittrich, Wreford and Moran 2016). In robust decision making approaches, multiple forecasts are integrated in the analysis, either by exploring the least vulnerable strategy or likelihood to perform well under various scenarios (“robust decision making”), identifying flexible strategies (“real options analysis”), devising strategies to diversify risk (“portfolio analysis”) or selecting no or low regret strategies. Dittrich, Wreford and Moran (2016) provide an overview of the conditions under which each of the decision making approaches is most appropriate, which – among other things – depends on the uncertainty involving the measures and the decision maker’s flexibility to change or reverse its decision in the future.

An approach to understand and deal with uncertainty and flexibility in decision making is real options analysis. Real options analysis is a methodology that aims to value the flexibility when deciding to invest, start a project, design a policy or execute an action. Dixit and Pindyck (1994) define real options as “the right but not the obligation to buy a [real] asset at some future time of its choosing”. The specification of “real” in a “real” option refers to investments in physical assets (e.g. infrastructure), as opposed to options in a financial context, such as a call or put option. The added value of real options analysis is most evident when it concerns large-scale, long-lived, costly investments that are irreversible in which the value of the investment is subject to uncertainty (Dixit and Pindyck 1994). Ginbo, Corato and Hoffmann (2021) provide a literature review on the application of real options analysis and the study of uncertainty in the context of CCM and CCA. They conclude real options analysis is able to account for multiple types of uncertainty simultaneously, such as market, climate, technological uncertainty. It also allows for the study of multiple agents and their interaction, such as the strategic interaction between the industry and policy makers.

8. CONCLUSION

In this report, we have examined the critical challenges and nuances associated with climate change adaptation (CCA) in connection to the evaluation of adaptation pathways. Recognizing the increasing importance of CCA, we have highlighted the limitations in current actions, emphasizing the need for more effective planning, financing, and implementation strategies. Most tools and methodologies for the valuation of CCA strategies focus on biophysical features of environments. Recognizing a significant knowledge deficit, particularly in economic dimensions, we emphasize the need for tools addressing cost considerations, aligning strategic vision with operational implementation, and enhancing the valuation of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS). The Nature Smart Cities Business model (NSC-BM) is proposed as a holistic tool for this purpose, and has been applied in other projects with municipalities.

Within TransformAr, the case study in Lappeenranta demonstrates the application of the NSC-BM to evaluate the proposed NBS. The tool provides a nuanced understanding, quantifying and monetizing ecosystem services to facilitate cost-benefit analyses. The results showcase the added value of investing in NBS, emphasizing the importance of qualitative, quantitative, and monetary assessments. The report acknowledges challenges, such as the exclusion of indirect project costs, and presents insights into the monetary implications of maintenance costs and benefits. In the reflection of this case study, we observed that these decision-support tools with regards to NBS are not mainstreamed. This underscores the need for intuitive and easily communicable tools, such as the provided factsheets with the tool.

This report outlines the ongoing efforts in assessing the anticipated impacts of transformative solutions, serving as a vital component of ex ante evaluation. The current NSC-BM tool can be used in other territories for rapid general estimates, which can be refined with minor data and parameter adjustments. By tailoring the input data and parameters to specific local contexts, the NSC-BM becomes a versatile tool for assessing NBS in different regions. Furthermore, the methodology may be extended beyond individual (nature based) solutions to enable a comprehensive analysis of RSP. In the evaluation of CCA measures apart from NBS, the current model and approach are applicable when these can be linked to the effectiveness of NBS. If such CCA measures are not related to the effectiveness of NBS, one should assess the different levels within the valuation pyramid (qualitative, quantitative and monetary, see Figure 11), and consider in what detail impacts can and should be evaluated.

The focus in this report is on predicting and forecasting the expected investment and maintenance costs, and anticipated benefits of a NBS. Future research directions involve the comparison of anticipated outcomes with actual results, supporting an iterative process of learning, refining methodologies, and optimizing decision-making processes.

In essence, this report contributes to the evaluation of RSP and, more specifically, NBS. The integration of macro and micro-level evaluations will strengthen this approach, and make it a valuable resource for informed decision-making in the face of a changing climate.

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APPENDICES

NSC-BM Factsheets for Lappeenranta case study

The output of the NSC-BM for the Lappeenranta case study is provided in the three sections below (Factsheet Lappeenranta Baseline vs Lappeenranta NBS, Factsheet Lappeenranta Baseline vs Lappeenranta Grey, and Factsheet Lappeenranta NBS vs Lappeenranta Grey).

After the title page, an overview of the selected ES and the two scenarios that are compared is provided. The remaining three pages of each report shows the output of the report. The output consists of a MCA considering selected outputs qualitatively, quantitatively and monetarily. The third page shows an overview a spider diagram, the fourth shows quantitative and qualitative descriptions of the selected ES in each scenario. Finally, the monetized output is shown: investment cost, annual maintenance cost and annual benefits.

When interpreting the monetized benefits, it is crucial to recognize that these are inherently tied to the specific geographic location under consideration. Location-dependent factors, such as local market prices, play a pivotal role in shaping the economic landscape. The monetization of benefits also varies significantly based on the chosen discount rate, reflecting the time value of money, and the price level. Therefore, it is important to consider these location- and time-specific variables when interpreting the factsheets provided by the NSC-BM.

Factsheet Lappeenranta Baseline vs Lappeenranta NBS

Business Case Factsheet

LAPPEENRANTA

city/urban
Landscape

1758
Project Area

1000
Number of inhabitant
Image of project area

Description

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Scenario Comparison

BASELINE SCENARIO

This is the initial state of Koulukatu street, where the entire street and its stormwater is connected to the sewage system.

LAPPEENRANTA NBS

The nature-based solution will be implemented. Existing green patches of lawn will be redesigned, and a larger retention area is to be placed. Further, 470 m² of surface area will be detached from the sewage system, which should result in lower risks of pluvial flooding.

Ecosystem Services

Food

Materials

Education and raising awareness

Habitat for biodiversity

Carbon sequestration

Physical and mental health

Noise pollution

Aesthetic appreciation

Attractor for companies and investm

Air filtering

Micro climate regulation

Recreation, and Tourism by external visitors

Social cohesion

Real estate prices

Water retention and infiltration

Selected Parameters

Currency €		BASELINE SCENARIO	LAPPEENRANTA NBS
	Water retention	272.78 m3/yr	413.00 m3/yr
	Air Filtering	5.56 kg/yr	6.27 kg/yr
	Carbon sequestration	97 kg/yr	108 kg/yr
		SW - Index 1.98	SW - Index 3.99
Aesthetic appreciation			
	Does this scenario provide an aesthetically attractive place to live or work in?	To a limited extent	To some extent
	Do people value the area for its contribution to the local landscape or streetscape?	To a limited extent	To some extent
	Does this scenario make outdoor activities more enjoyable?	To a limited extent	To a limited extent
	Does this scenario include an attractive mix of different landscape elements?	Not at all	To a limited extent
	Does this scenario promote people's engagement with the natural world?	Not at all	To some extent
	Does this scenario create, or add to, a sense of place and visual identity?	Not at all	To a limited extent
	Do people enjoy spending time in and around this scenario area?	Not at all	Not at all
	Does this scenario contribute towards civic pride in the locality?	Not at all	To a limited extent

Financial Information

BASELINE SCENARIO

LAPPEENRANTA NBS

Factsheet Lappeenranta Baseline vs Lappeenranta Grey

Business Case Factsheet

LAPPEENRANTA

city/urban
Landscape

1758
Project Area

1000
Number of inhabitant
Image of project area

Description

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Scenario Comparison

BASELINE SCENARIO

This is the initial state of Koulukatu street, where the entire street and its stormwater is connected to the sewage system.

LAPPEENRANTA GREY

Through this hypothetical scenario, we compare the current state and the NBS scenario with the situation as it would be if the street would only be composed of grey infrastructure.

Ecosystem Services

Food

Materials

Education and raising awareness

Habitat for biodiversity

Carbon sequestration

Physical and mental health

Noise pollution

Aesthetic appreciation

Attractor for companies and investm

Air filtering

Micro climate regulation

Recreation, and Tourism by external visitors

Social cohesion

Real estate prices

Water retention and infiltration

Selected Parameters

Currency €		BASELINE SCENARIO	LAPPEENRANTA GREY
	Water retention	272.78 m3/yr	21.59 m3/yr
	Air Filtering	5.56 kg/yr	0.00 kg/yr
	Carbon sequestration	97 kg/yr	00 kg/yr
		SW - Index 1.98	SW - Index FALSE
Aesthetic appreciation			
	Does this scenario provide an aesthetically attractive place to live or work in?	To a limited extent	Not at all
	Do people value the area for its contribution to the local landscape or streetscape?	To a limited extent	Not at all
	Does this scenario make outdoor activities more enjoyable?	To a limited extent	Not at all
	Does this scenario include an attractive mix of different landscape elements?	Not at all	Not at all
	Does this scenario promote people's engagement with the natural world?	Not at all	Not at all
	Does this scenario create, or add to, a sense of place and visual identity?	Not at all	Not at all
	Do people enjoy spending time in and around this scenario area?	Not at all	Not at all
	Does this scenario contribute towards civic pride in the locality?	Not at all	Not at all

Financial Information

BASILINE SCENARIO

LAPPEENRANTA GREY

Factsheet Lappeenranta NBS vs Lappeenranta Grey

Business Case Factsheet

LAPPEENRANTA

city/urban
Landscape

1758
Project Area

1000
Number of inhabitant
Image of project area

Description

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Scenario Comparison

LAPPEENRANTA GREY

Through this hypothetical scenario, we compare the current state and the NBS scenario with the situation as it would be if the street would only be composed of grey infrastructure.

LAPPEENRANTA NBS

The nature-based solution will be implemented. Existing green patches of lawn will be redesigned, and a larger retention area is to be placed. Further, 470 m² of surface area will be detached from the sewage system, which should result in lower risks of pluvial flooding.

Ecosystem Services

Food

Materials

Education and raising awareness

Habitat for biodiversity

Carbon sequestration

Physical and mental health

Noise pollution

Aesthetic appreciation

Attractor for companies and investment

Air filtering

Micro climate regulation

Recreation, and Tourism by external visitors

Social cohesion

Real estate prices

Water retention and infiltration

Selected Parameters

Currency		€	LAPPEENRANTA GREY	LAPPEENRANTA NBS
	Water retention		21.59 m3/yr	867.36 m3/yr
	Air Filtering		0.00 kg/yr	6.27 kg/yr
	Carbon sequestration		00 kg/yr	108 kg/yr
			SW - Index FALSE	SW - Index 3.99
	Aesthetic appreciation			
	Does this scenario provide an aesthetically attractive place to live or work in?	Not at all	To some extent	
	Do people value the area for its contribution to the local landscape or streetscape?	Not at all	To some extent	
	Does this scenario make outdoor activities more enjoyable?	Not at all	To a limited extent	
	Does this scenario include an attractive mix of different landscape elements?	Not at all	To a limited extent	
	Does this scenario promote people's engagement with the natural world?	Not at all	To some extent	
	Does this scenario create, or add to, a sense of place and visual identity?	Not at all	To a limited extent	
	Do people enjoy spending time in and around this scenario area?	Not at all	Not at all	
Does this scenario contribute towards civic pride in the locality?	Not at all	To a limited extent		

Financial Information

LAPPEENRANTA GREY

LAPPEENRANTA NBS

